
**SHRI CHATRAPATI SHIVAJI PUBLIC LIBRARY, SAVARDE - A
STUDY**

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Abstract:

This study is committed to determining the functions, services, collections, and facilities provided by Sri Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library, Savarde. The purpose of the study is to determine the objectives of this library. The study also focuses on the development and growth of the Shree Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library. Various services offered by this library to its readers have been studied. What kind of readers are there in this library has been studied by the researchers. The researcher has reviewed the development of the Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Libraries from its establishment to till now.

Key Words: Public library, Library Services, Library Users, Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library

Introduction:

Public libraries play a vital role in developing a person to become a better person. The public library provides services to all people of age, sex, caste, religion, education, and social studies. All users get reading materials relevant to their needs and requirements in public libraries. The purpose of the public library is to provide various information resources and services for democracy and society development, including education, information, and personal development of people of different groups. A public library is a non-commercial library accessible to the public. The main objective is to provide free reading material to the public. A public library is a powerful source of information for education and culture. Efforts are being made to create a public

library in every village area in India. All these services are provided at a moderate cost to make public libraries in Maharashtra accessible to all. According to the level of the public library, they are given a subsidy by the government. Using the said libraries can increase their reading material. It has been discussed how they are provided through various concessions given to public libraries by the government.

Public Library: An Overview

Public libraries are a powerhouse of knowledge and are meant for use by the general public. The public library helps to develop an interest in reading among all kinds of readers. According to Dr. S.R. Ranganathan, the father of the Library movement In India, define as “the public

library is open to any member of the public and annually free of any charge paid as so much service” (Ranganathan,1950). “The public library, the local gateway to knowledge, provides a basic condition for lifelong learning, independent decision-making and cultural development of the individual and social groups” (IFLA/UNESCO Public Library Manifesto, 1994).

Shri Chatrapati Shivaji Public Library: An Overview:

Shri Chatrapati Shivaji Public Library was established by Shri Bhagat Singh Tarun Mandal in the year 1976 and was recognized as a “D” grade in 1978. This library got an “A” grade in 2011. The area of the library building is 2000 sq. ft. And there are six different separate sections, 1) Child reader section 2) Reference section 3) Woman’s section 4) Library section 5) Newspaper reading section 6) Periodical and magazine section. At present library has a collection of 22353 books (till 20 March 2022), 78 periodicals, and 16 daily newspapers & magazines.

Objective of this Study:

This study is being conducted to understand the functioning, development and services provided to the users by Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library.

1) To review the development of Shri. Chatrapati Shivaji Public Library

Review of literature:

The majority of people in India live in rural areas and new technologies are not available in remote areas, thus creating a huge gap in knowledge and libraries in rural areas. Today the Internet and web technologies are the new means of

communication. Advances in communication technologies (ICT) can connect remote people to interact with public libraries and civil society. Technology can be used to improve and promote existing library services. An attempt is made here to propose ICT for urban communities as well as public libraries operating in Indian states with suitable library extension programs to help the entire rural population. (Ghosh, 2005) This study is committed to determining the organization and functioning of Pratap Public Library, Karnal (Haryana). The purpose of the study was to determine the aims and objectives of the library. Public libraries are established by the people for the benefit of the people. Among all other types of libraries developed by society in modern times, public libraries are the most popular libraries because of the functions they perform. They have a great contribution to the welfare of society. (Narula, 2017). In this chapter, a thorough account of how the library was established in ancient India is given. Public libraries started to appear all throughout the world at the same time when publishing, literacy, and education all grew. Every nation has a unique public library history. The growth of public libraries has been aided by emperors, the affluent, and philanthropists. Emperors, wealthy businessmen, and scholars were primarily responsible for funding the establishment of libraries in ancient India. The emperors and kings of India funded academics. There is proof that libraries existed in their current form as early as the sixth century AD. With a sizable collection of manuscripts spanning the breadth of knowledge, the renowned Nalanda University in Bihar has its own wonderful library. (Wani, 2008).

Scope & Limitation:

This is a scholarly attempt to know the practices of Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library. Discusses how the practices adopted at the Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library can increase the use of libraries and what steps can be taken to improve the existing services if they are not satisfactory. This study is limited to Sri Chhatrapati Shivaji Public Library only.

Problems:

Shivaji Public Library was established in Sawarde, a small village in Panhala Taluka of Kolhapur District. Shivaji Public Library is a big library. Books, newspapers, and magazines Collection of Shivaji Public Library was good. Although this library is in a rural area, it has a good collection of books related to libraries in urban areas. However, the readership of this Garatha is less so this library needs to be brought into the limelight so that more users can take advantage of this library. Libraries should focus on increasing readership.

Methodology:

The case study method is use for this study. Research methods like Cluster sampling method, lottery method, and interview techniques have been used to collect data. The collected data is present using different tables and figures.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Information from 7.1 to 7.4 has been obtained from the librarian of Shivaji library

1. Collection of books from 1978 to 2022

Collection of books at grading time

Table No.1

Year	Library Grade	No. of Books
1978	D	426
1986	C	1403
2003	B	6810
2011	A	16280
2022	A	22353

Fig.1

Above table and fig. shows that, in year 1978 library got grade D status and that time they have 426 books. In year 1986 library got grade C and that time they have 1403 books. In year 2003 library got grade B status and that time they have 6810 books. In year 2011 library got grade A status and that time they have 16280 books. At present time (March 2022) library is in grade A status and having a 22353 books.

2. Difference in the collection of books from 1976 to 2022:**Table No. 2**

Year	Difference in grade	No. of books from last grade	Difference of books in last grade
1976-1978	No Grade - Grade D	0-426	426
1978-1986	Grade D - Grade C	427-1403	977
1986-2003	Grade C - Grade B	1404-6810	5407
2003-2011	Grade B - Grade A	6811-16280	9470
2011-2022	Grade A	16281-22353	6073

Fig. 2

Above table and fig. shows that, this library collection increase by 426 books in first 2 years. After this library got D grade in 1978, library collection increases by 977 books till they got grade C in 1986. Then library is recognized as grade B in year 2003, library collection is increased by 5407 books grade C to grade B i.e. from 1986 to 2003. In 2011 library is recognized as grade A library, at that time library manages to increase collection of books up to 9470 from grade B (i.e. 1986 to 2003) At present time in 2022 library has collection of 22353 books i.e. library increased their collection by 6073 books from the year 2011.

3. Number of Newspapers per grade from 1978 to 2022:

Table No. 3

Year	Grade of library	No. of Newspapers
1978	D	4
1986	C	4
2003	B	6
2011	A	16
2022	A	16

Fig. 3

Above table and fig. shows us, the number of Newspapers from grade D to grade A. In 1978, when library is recognized as grade D status library has 4 newspapers. In 1986 library has also 4 different newspapers. In 2003, when library is recognized as grade B they has 6 different newspapers. In 2011, library has got grade A status and that time library has 16 different newspapers daily. At present time in 2022 library has 16 different kinds of Newspapers daily.

4. Number of periodicals per grade from 1978 to 2022:

Table No.4

Year	Grade of library	No. of periodicals
1978	D	6
1986	C	6
2003	B	20
2011	A	58
2022	A	78

Fig. 4

Above table and fig. show us number of Periodicals library has. In year 1978 and 1986 library has 6 different periodicals. In 2003 number of periodicals increased from 6 to 20. In 2011, as the library got grade A status, number of periodicals are increased up to 52 periodicals. At present time in 2022, library has huge collection of 78 different types of Periodicals.

Conclusion:

Shri. Chh. Shivaji Public Library was established in 1976 and they got grade D in 1978. From 1978 to 2022 library's growth is satisfactory. Time to time they upgrade their collections with respect to books, magazines and periodicals and also newspapers.

Recommendation:

1. Card system is used for exchange of books, it needs to be changed and updated as an online system.
2. Books are kept according to acquisition numbers, they need to be changed and updated as DDC or UDC or any other classification system.
3. The library should be computerized.

Reference:

1. UNESCO IFLA. (1994). *IFLA/UNESCO Public Library Manifesto 1994*. Retrieved from

<https://repository.ifla.org/handle/123456789/168>

2. Ranganathan, S.R. (1950). *Library Development Plan: Thirty Years Programmes for India, with Draft Library Bills for the Union and the Constituent States*. Delhi: University of Delhi Press
3. Ghosh, M. (2005). The public library system in India: challenges and opportunities. *Library Review*, 54(3), 180-191. DOI: 10.1108/00242530510588935
4. Mahesh Gaikwad. (2015) *Usage of Library Collection by college Students at Arts and Commerce College, Madha: A Study*. Conference: Challenges of Academic Libraries in Digital Environment at R RPatil College, Savlaj at: Savlaj, Maharashtra. Abhiyanta Publication
5. Narula, S. (2017). ORGANISATION & WORKING OF THE PRATAP PUBLIC LIBRARY, KARNAL, HARYANA: A CASE STUDY. *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, 3(7), 106-113.
6. Ole Pors, N. (2006). The public library and students' information needs. *New LibraryWorld*, 107(7/8), 275-285. DOI: 10.1108/03074800610677263
7. Wani, Z. (2008). Development of Public Libraries in India. *Library Philosophy and Practice (E-Journal)*, (165), 1-10.